

Research Article

Waste-to-Watts: Harnessing Waste Carbon for Hydrogen Evolution

N.A. Asli^{1,*}, H. Omar², N.F. Rosman³, N.S.A. Malek⁴, M.S.N. Durratun⁵, A. N. Afaah⁶, and Nadya Hajar⁷

¹ Centre for Functional Materials and Nanotechnology, Institute of Science, Universiti Teknologi MARA, 40450, Shah Alam, Selangor, Malaysia; asnida1462@uitm.edu.my; ORCID ID (<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9426-9227>)

² Centre for Functional Materials and Nanotechnology, Institute of Science, Universiti Teknologi MARA, 40450, Shah Alam, Selangor, Malaysia; email; ORCID ID (<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6861-1738>)

³ Centre for Functional Materials and Nanotechnology, Institute of Science, Universiti Teknologi MARA, 40450, Shah Alam, Selangor, Malaysia; hanaadrilldanielle143@gmail.com; ORCID ID (<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7879-3130>)

⁴ Centre for Functional Materials and Nanotechnology, Institute of Science, Universiti Teknologi MARA, 40450, Shah Alam, Selangor, Malaysia; email; ORCID ID (<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6118-3574>)

⁵ Centre for Functional Materials and Nanotechnology, Institute of Science, Universiti Teknologi MARA, 40450, Shah Alam, Selangor, Malaysia; durratunnasihah028899@gmail.com; ORCID ID (<https://orcid.org/0009-0007-2646-4988>)

⁶ Centre for Functional Materials and Nanotechnology, Institute of Science, Universiti Teknologi MARA, 40450, Shah Alam, Selangor, Malaysia; afaahabdullah@yahoo.com; ORCID ID (<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9757-8807>)

⁷ Department of Food Technology, Faculty of Applied Sciences, Universiti Teknologi MARA, Cawangan Negeri Sembilan, Kuala Pilah Campus, Kuala Pilah, Negeri Sembilan, Malaysia; nadya1844@uitm.edu.my; ORCID ID (<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9843-4733>)

* Correspondence: asnida1462@uitm.edu.my

Abstract: Graphene, a remarkable two-dimensional (2D) material has emerged as a significant advancement following the development of carbon nanotubes. The reliance on petroleum-derived materials has raised various sustainability concerns, prompting the exploration of innovative methods for graphene production and waste management. This study explores the characterization of graphene synthesized from carbon-rich waste materials using both bottom-up and top-down approaches. Since graphene consists mainly of chemically bonded carbon atoms, the starting materials must be high in carbon content. This study also focuses on natural and synthetic waste sources, including waste cooking oil, waste engine oil, coconut shells, and plastics, which offer significant potential for high-quality graphene production. Utilizing these waste materials can reduce landfill waste and mitigate toxic land contamination. Producing graphene from abundant waste could represent a transformative advancement in its applications.

Keywords: waste carbon source; graphene; hydrogen evolution.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Graphene, a single layer of carbon atoms arranged in a honeycomb lattice, possesses exceptional electrical, thermal, and mechanical properties. Its high carrier mobility and thermal conductivity make it a promising material for various applications (Das, Sudhagar, Kang, & Choi, 2014; Lavin-Lopez et al., 2019). It has a unique structure that is similar to interconnected benzene rings, that

makes it a promising materials through various application including electronics and energy storage(Chandrantha et al., 2024). It is also an allotrope of carbon, a flat sheet of atoms bonded together in hexagonal pattern. Graphene's exceptional properties, which include its high transparency, make it a prime candidate for various electronic applications such as LEDs, solar cells, transistor and displays (Ramos Ferrer, Mace, Thomas, & Jeon, 2017). Furthermore, when multiple layers of graphene are stacked together, they formed graphite which are a more complicated compound. Graphene and graphite can be chemically treated to form graphene oxide (GO) and graphite oxide, respectively(Gao, Alemany, Ci, & Ajayan, 2009). This process introduces oxygen-containing groups like carbonyl, hydroxyl, and carboxyl onto the carbon structure. A diverse range of carbon-containing materials can serve as precursors for graphene synthesis(Yan et al., 2020). Graphene's exceptional properties and structure have captivated the interest of numerous scientists and engineers in recent decades, making it a subject of intensive research. Since graphene is has been in focus for researcher and it is rare in nature, its synthesis has been a topic of much discussion. Synthesis is currently the signifies method for producing graphene-based material.

While natural resources are limited, waste materials such as industrial waste, agricultural waste, and biomass waste offer sustainable alternatives for the mass production of graphene. Waste refers to materials that are discarded after use due to their lack of utility(Golueke & Diaz, 1991). Waste can be categorized into various types, including hazardous materials, radioactive substances, wastewater, and industrial byproducts (Nixon & Murphy, 1998; Saleh & Eskander, 2020). Improper waste disposal leads to various environmental pollutants, including water, air, and soil contamination(Ferronato & Torretta, 2019). Worldwide, approximately 10 billion tons of solid waste are generated annually, and this amount is projected to increase to 27 billion tons by 2050(Chen, Bodirsky, Krueger, Mishra, & Popp, 2020; Hoornweg, Bhada-Tata, & Kennedy, 2015). There are various of techniques to synthesis graphene including chemical vapour deposition (CVD), Hummers' method and pyrolysis from this various precursor (Omar et al., 2022). This research focuses on examining different methods for producing graphene from various carbon sources and its potential towards hydrogen production. Several techniques, such as chemical vapor deposition (CVD), Hummer's method, liquid-phase exfoliation (LPE), and pyrolysis, can be employed to synthesize graphene from different precursors. Each technique requires different precursors, undergoes different processes, and yields different products of graphene (Mbayachi et al., 2021).

2. CARBON SOURCE

2.1 Waste Engine Oil

Waste engine oil (WEO), a byproduct of engine maintenance, is a rich source of carbon (Abdullah et al., 2020; Kalanidhi & Nagaraaj, 2022) for graphene production. Despite its environmental concerns due to high levels of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) (Nurfazianawatie et al., 2023) and metals, WEO has a lower flash point compared to fresh oil making it easier to vaporize (Nurfazianawatie et al., 2023). This study optimized the chemical vapor deposition (CVD) process using WEO as a precursor and nickel as a substrate. The results indicate that WEO can be successfully converted into graphene with promising properties.

2.2 Plastic Waste

Plastic waste can be a valuable source of carbon for graphene production. This study demonstrates a scalable and cost-effective method to convert polymeric plastics like PE, PP, and PS into graphene nanosheets (Pandey et al., 2019)(Nurfazianawatie et al., 2023). The process involves shredding, washing, drying, mixing with bentonite, and pyrolysis (Pandey et al.,

2019)(Nurfazianawatie et al., 2023). This approach offers a sustainable solution to the plastic waste problem, providing both environmental benefits and economic value.

2.3 Coconut shells

Coconut shells are the inedible, outer part of coconuts and are considered agricultural waste(Somashekhar, Naik, Nayak, & Rahul, 2018). When ground into powder, coconut shells offer several advantages over other materials, including affordability, renewability, low density, and environmental friendliness (Somashekhar et al., 2018). Combining coconut shell powder with epoxy resins enhances their properties, opening up new possibilities for their application. Graphite powder can be produced through graphitization by pyrolyzing coconut shells. Graphite powder can then be further processed using Hummer's method to create graphene oxide (GO)(Sujiono, Zabrian, Dahlan, Amin, & Agus, 2020).

2.4 Waste Cooking Oil

Waste cooking oil (WCO), often referred to as 'waste cooking oil' or 'used cooking oil,' is a bio-waste rich in carbon and fatty acids (Allah & Alexaandru, 2016; Awogbemi et al., 2019; Patel et al., 2019; Tsai, 2019). Its carbon content can vary due to high-temperature reactions during frying, reaching 76.95%, which is higher than that of refined palm oil at 68.81% (Nurfazianawatie et al., 2023b; Nurfazianawatie et al., 2020). Though classified as household waste, WCO can be a valuable secondary raw resource if managed properly (de Feo et al., 2020). Graphene can be produced from waste cooking oil using the chemical vapour deposition (CVD) method by modifying the parameters of the CVD synthesis profile to obtain optimum graphene samples (Deng et al., 2019).

3. METHOD OF SYNTHESIZE

3.1 Chemical Vapor Deposition (CVD)

CVD is a technique employed in the semiconductor sector to produce high-quality, solid, thin-film materials, especially for transition metal graphene sheets. The procedure entails gas-phase mixtures and surface reactions, with carrier gases transporting volatile precursors to the reaction zone. The method generates a thin substrate coating and gaseous byproducts, incorporating many systems such as carrier gas, gas supply, gas distribution, energy source, and exhaust gas purification.

The precursor carbon source is gaseous. Waste cooking oil (WCO) is heated using plasma or a resistivity heated coil, and an inert gas is supplied into the reaction chamber to start the chemical reaction (Nurfazianawatie et al., 2020). The impact of CVD chamber gas flow on graphene thickness homogeneity and accurate gas flow control for uniform and high-quality growth (Deng et al., 2019). Due to their inertness, nickel and copper catalysts are used to deposit films on the substrate during CVD. Cleaning metal surfaces using hydrogen or argon gases removes oxides. A graphene sheet is deposited on the substrate (Shams et al.,2015). The heated precursor gas decomposes into carbon (the thin film) and a byproduct gas throughout the process (Deng et al., 2019).

3.2 Hummers' Method

Hummers' method makes graphene from graphite oxide. William S. Hummers and Richard E. Offeman improved the Staudenmaier method in 1958. Hummer uses potassium permanganate (KMnO₄) instead of hazardous potassium chlorate (KClO₄) (Alkhouzaam et al., 2020). This method only provides graphite oxide, which needs pyrolysis (Omar et al., 2023). Synthesis can produce graphene, graphene oxide (GO), and GO reduction (Adetayo & Runsewe, 2019). Hummer's process

uses sulphuric acid (H_2SO_4) and sodium nitrate (NaNO_3) as reactants and potassium permanganate (KMnO_4) to oxidise graphite powder in 24 h (Alkhouzaam et al., 2020).

Alkhouzaam et al. (2020) suggest combining H_2SO_4 and H_3PO_4 in various volume ratios in an ice bath for a few minutes. Hummer's graphite oxide production is shown in Fig. 1. Zhu et al. (2022) synthesised high-quality, safer, and less toxic rGO with less concentrated acid sulphuric. Oxidation added graphite oxygen functional groups such hydroxyl groups (OH) (Al-Gaashani, Najjar, Zakaria, Mansour, & Atieh, 2019).

Figure 1. Schematic diagram of Changing solution color that signifies the process in Hummers' method

4. POTENTIAL APPLICATION IN HYDROGEN ENERGY

4.1 Hydrogen evolution reaction (HER) using reduced graphene oxide-based coconut shell charcoal for Hydrogen Production

Renewable energy has become attentions to researcher nowadays as its support the world campaign on sustainability. Hydrogen energy which applications such as in fuel cell is known as a promising renewable and clean energy. Coconut shell (CS) is one of biomass that can be obtained abundantly especially Malaysia as it contains more than 50% of carbon that suitable as carbon precursor. Composites catalyst especially supported by graphene based material as catalyst, either its binary or ternary systems were observed to be an effective method for improving the hydrogen evolution reaction (Li et al., 2022). Figure 2 present the HER activity current density vs over potential graph for rGO-based coconut shell charcoal (CSC) nanocomposites with iron (III) oxide and copper (II) oxide. The synthesis of rGO using carbon precursor in nanosize in many forms such as nanoparticle, nanopowder or nanoflakes has shown a significant changes in the HER performance as it increase the surface to volume ratio for the electrochemical process. The one byproduct combustion is environmental friendly as it is pollution free water which makes H_2 as a potential materials for future low carbon energy system.

Figure 2. HER performance of rGO nanocomposites comparison for four different materials

Table 1 tabulated the over potential of for four different sample as electrocatalyst for HER performance in acidic medium. Carbon based materials has shown an excellent structural properties and conductivity that prove an efficient performance for HER catalyst (Luo et al., 2019). The value of η_{10} over potential was observed to reduce to a smaller value.

Table 1. Over potential value for different nanocomposites as electrocatalyst using rGO based coconut shell charcoal

Samples	η_{10} over potential (mV)	Medium
rGO	877	0.5 H ₂ SO ₄
rGO/Fe ₂ O ₃	856	
rGO/CuO	821	
rGO/Fe ₂ O ₃ /CuO	668	

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